

**THE INFLUENCE OF LEATHER PUPPET PICTURE ON THE
IMPROVEMENT OF RETELLING STORY ABILITY OF 7TH GRADE
MENTAL RETARDED STUDENTS IN SLB C SETYA DARMA
SURAKARTA, INDONESIA YEAR 2016/2017**

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to identify the influence of leather puppet picture on the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta. All 7th grade students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta are used as the population and sample for this research. This research is a kind of experimental research with One Group Pretest-Posttest Design. Technique of collecting data is conducted by using oral test as the way to collect the students' ability of retelling story. To analyze the data, Statistical Quantitative non Parametric is used as the technique. This technique is also called Wilcoxon Sign Rank Test, which is given a Z symbol. Wilcoxon test is used to test 2 variables, items: before treatment and after treatment, with 0.05 significance level. The result of this research proves that the using of leather puppet picture are effect for the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta 2016/2017.

Keywords: leather puppet picture, retelling story ability of mental retarded students

1. Introduction

Language is a communicating media for human by expressing minds, information, attitude, and feelings. Language is very important in daily life. It will be learnt from we were born until adulthood in the environment of both family and school (Guntur, 2008: 14). For some people, language is just merely a communication media. This assumption makes people emphasize on aspect of verbal communication rather than writing

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communication. In the other word, people assume that verbal communication is way more important than communication in the form of writing (Mahayana, 2008: 1).

We learn language, especially in the subject of Bahasa Indonesia. According to Guntur (2008: 20), in learning Bahasa Indonesia, it is given knowledge and ability of language covering for components, namely: listening, reading, writing, and speaking. Basically, every student has different level of language ability. Therefore, Bahasa Indonesia is expected to help students in developing needed language ability, not only for communication but also for understanding every kind of value and knowledge.

This research problem is on 7th grade mental retarded student in SMPLB who are not fluent enough in language ability, especially on retelling story. The development of retelling story ability should be conducted effectively for students as early as possible, so that they can receive materials in school well and they can develop their speaking skill well. It is different with normal children. Mental retarded students are included in individuals needing special needs. One of their characteristics is having low intelligence. It makes their ability of language is disturbed, so that their ability in speaking and retelling simple story needs special training in education.

Based on Educational Psychology book, H.C. Witherington in Anunurrahman (2012: 12), learning is a changing in personality expressing as a new pattern of ability, attitude, habit, personality or understanding. In this term, someone is called learning if he or she realizes something that she or he did not know before.

Based on this explanation, researcher chooses a suitable media as learning media and as an effort to improve retelling story ability of 5 students of 7th grade mental retarded students SMPLB in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta. This ability is important to be developed even it is still in level of junior high school.

According to elaboration above, researcher is interested to conduct a research to improve retelling story ability of Bahasa Indonesia of mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta by observing its causes, influence, and implication as special factors. This research will examine *"The Influence of leather puppet picture on the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017"*.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Research Design

Experimental research method based on Sugiyono (2013: 107) can be defined as a research method used to figure out the influence of particular treatment for something

else in controlled condition. This is a part of quantitative research having special characteristic, especially its control group. Experimental research method according to Sukardi (2013: 179) can be defined as a systematic method to build causal-effect relationship. Generally, this research is used to answer questions related to a controlled condition. Besides, experiment research is conducted to arrange a situation where the influence of some variables to dependent variable can be identified.

According to Sugiyono (2013: 108), there are some kinds of Pre Experimental Design, namely: One Shot Case Study, One Group Pretest- Posttest Design, and Intact-Group Comparison. Design used in this research was One Group Pretest-Posttest Design, where a group of subject is given treatment in a period of time. The measurement was done before and after treatment, and the differences between the result of first measurement (T1) and result of the second measurement (T2) is the influence of treatment given.

2.2 Research Variable

This research with title *“The Influence of leather puppet picture on the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017”* contains two variables, namely:

1. Independent Variable (X)

The independent variable in this research is leather puppet picture.

2. Dependent Variable (Y)

Dependent variable is variable influenced by dependent variable. The dependent variable in this research is retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta.

2.3 Technique of Collecting Data

Data in this research is indicator quality of retelling story ability of mental retarded students. Instrument used to collect the data in this research is test, validation sheets from contain and assessment experts.

2.4 Technique of Analyzing Data

Technique of analyzing data used in this research is quantitative descriptive analysis.

2.5 Procedure

Title of this research is *“The Influence of leather puppet picture on the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta*

Year 2016/2017". It contains two variables, namely: (1) independent variable: the influence of leather puppet, and (2) dependent variable: retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta. This research aims to test hypothesis said *"There is significant influence of the using of leather puppet to the development of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017"*.

The instrument used in this research is arranged based on research instrument's table of specification. Instrument used in this research is test, namely verbal test of retelling story. Validity of this instrument is tested to gain valid data. 3 lecturers validated the instrument. This research is conducted after the instrument and field preparations are done. This research is located in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta with 5 students of 7th grade mental retarded students on second semester year 2016/2017 as the subject.

This research is given one basic competence, namely explaining relation between content of story and social reality with the indicator of retelling the story in front of class. First data is collected by using arranging data. The next step is giving treatment by implementing leather puppet with retelling story ability. After treatment, research gave posttest to 7th grade of mental retarded students.

Final step of this research is analyzing the results of pretest and posttest. Before analyzing using Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test by helping of SPSS program 23rd version, first it is needed to explain data description of pretest and posttest with their histogram. After that, researcher analyses data and presents research findings. The final step is giving conclusion based on data.

3. Result

3.1 Description of the Data

1. Data of Students' Ability Before Treatment

This point contains data obtained from the result of treatment test. The data is obtained from the result of treatment test in the experiment. From the experiment, result is obtained as follows.

Table 1: Data of Pretest Score

Scorer Name	Students' Score					Total Score
	ST (1)	MG (2)	TF (3)	RZ (4)	SR (5)	
Abwatie (X)	11	7	6	9	14	47
Dina (Y)	12	6	6	8	14	46
Ida (Z)	13	12	13	15	27	70

2. Data of Students' Ability after Treatment

It contains data description of retelling story ability's score of mental retarded students after treatment. Result is obtained as follows.

Table 2: Data of Posttest Score

Scorer Name	Students' Score					Total Score
	ST (1)	MG (2)	TF (3)	RZ (4)	SR (5)	
Abwatie (X)	16	17	16	19	20	88
Dina (Y)	19	17	18	20	20	94
Ida (Z)	14	12	12	18	23	79

Researcher conducted research for 4-5 meetings. The first meeting is used as pretest. Second and third meeting is used as treatment, and the last meeting is used as posttest.

Table 3: Data of Pretest and Posttest Score

Statistics		Pretest	Posttest
N	Valid	3	3
	Missing	0	0
Mean		54.33	87.00
Median		47.00	88.00
Mode		46 ^a	79 ^a
Std. Deviation		13.577	7.550
Minimum		46	79
Maximum		70	94
Percentiles	25	46.00	79.00
	50	47.00	88.00
	75	70.00	94.00

Based on data description above, it can be seen that average score of retelling story ability of mental retarded student in pretest is 54.33 and average score of retelling story

ability of mental retarded student in posttest is 87.00. It means that there is difference result of pretest and posttest of retelling story ability.

3.2 Result of Hypothesis Test

To prove the hypothesis that there is significant influence of using leather puppet picture to the development of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017, it is used Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test as follows.

Table 4: Data Analysis Before and After Treatment

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pretest	5	9.40	3.209	6	14
Posttest	5	17.60	1.817	16	20

Table 5: Result of Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

Ranks

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
posttest - pretest	Negative Ranks	0 ^a	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	5 ^b	3.00	15.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	5		

a. posttest < pretest

b. posttest > pretest

c. posttest = pretest

Table 6: Result Test Statistics

Test Statistics^a

	posttest - pretest
Z	-2.060 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.039

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks.

Data above is processed by using SPSS 23rd Version. Based on ranks table, it is known that there is none negative ranks. There are 5 positive ranks and none same ranks. Result of hypothesis test about pretest and posttest score of retelling story ability is $Z = -$

2.060 with Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) = 0,039 with significant level (α) 5%. Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value = 0,039 $< \alpha = 0,05$ then, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that there is positive difference on retelling story ability score of mental retarded students before and after treatment by using leather puppet picture.

It can be concluded that the using of leather puppet picture influences the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017.

4. Discussion

After conducting data analysis to test hypothesis, discussion is the next step need to be done. The discussion is as follows. Hypothesis is said "There is significant influence of the using of leather puppet to the development of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017". The using of leather puppet picture makes retelling story of Bahasa Indonesia is easier for mental retarded students. This media becomes alternative learning media for retelling story of Bahasa Indonesia.

Mental retarded students have low retelling story or speaking ability. According to Rochyadi in Apriyanto (2012: 49), there are two things needed to be concerned related to communication process disorder. First is speaking disorder that an individual is hard to articulate language well. Second is language disorder which is more serious than previous one that a child is hard in understanding and using vocabulary and hard in understanding syntaxes rules of language used.

The using of leather puppet picture ease mental retarded to improve their retelling story ability researcher modified leather puppet picture became more attractive with characteristics of mental retarded children. Those modifications are giving attractive color on the puppet picture, providing stick on the puppet that makes children easier to use. The advantages of this media are firstly; its color and picture are attractive. Secondly, it eases children to retell their story. Thirdly, it is fun to use leather puppet picture. It can be concluded that the using of leather puppet picture is effective to reach learning objective.

There are also some disadvantages of this media. It consumes time to make this media. It also needs high cost to buy some tools like Styrofoam cutter and Styrofoam itself. Lastly, it also needs to search for proper picture with the theme; even researchers need to draw it by themselves.

It can be known that there is significant difference of average score of retelling story ability between first test (before giving treatment) and last test (after giving treatment). The average score of retelling story ability of mental retarded student in pretest is 54.33 and average score of retelling story ability of mental retarded student in posttest is 87.00. It means that there is improvement of mental retarded students' ability of retelling story. Result of hypothesis test about pretest and posttest score of retelling story ability is $Z = -2.060$ with $\text{Asymp.Sig. (2-tailed)} = 0,039$ with significant level (α) 5%. $\text{Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) value} = 0,039 < \alpha = 0,05$ then, Null Hypothesis (H_0) stating that there is no influence of the using of leather puppet to the development of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017 is rejected. Alternative hypothesis (H_a) stating that there is influence of the using of leather puppet to the development of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017 is accepted.

It can be concluded that the using of leather puppet picture is influence significantly to improve retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta Year 2016/2017 since this media is easy and attractive to play.

5. Conclusion

After elaborating research result of leather puppet picture to improve retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta, it can be concluded that there is positive influence of the using of leather puppet picture for the improvement of retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retardation students year 2016/2017.

6. Implication

Implication of this research can be in the form of theoretically and practically. Those implications are as follows.

1. Theoretical Implication

The result of this research theoretically can improve knowledge for researcher and teachers about leather puppet picture as one alternative media to improve retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students.

2. Practical Implication

The result of this research practically can be implemented is the learning process by using leather puppet picture as an effort to improve retelling story ability of 7th grade mental retarded students in SLB C Setya Darma Surakarta.

7. Suggestions

Based on the conclusion, it can be suggested that:

1. For Headmaster

School is expected to motivate teacher to use leather puppet picture so, it can be implemented as one media in school for mental retarded students.

2. For Teachers

Teachers are expected to apply this media as one of the learning media to improve retelling story ability of mental retarded students.

3. For Students

Students, with help from teacher, are expected to use leather puppet picture optimally by improving their retelling story ability, so that they can also get fun learning experience.

4. For Further Researcher

Further researchers are expected to conduct further research so, they can give more references about leather puppet picture to improve retelling story ability.

References

1. Apriyanto, Nunung. (2012). *SelukBelukTunagrahita&StrategiPembelajarannya*. Jogjakarta: Javalitera.
2. Aunurrahman. (2012). *BelajardanPembelajaran*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
3. Guntur T, Henry. (2008). *BerbicaraSebagaiSuatuKeterampilanBerbahasa*. Bandung: PT. Angkasa.
4. Mahayana, Maman S. (2008). *Bahasa Indonesia Kreatif*. Jakarta: Penaku.
5. Sugiyono. (2013). *MetodePenelitianPendidikan*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
6. Sukardi. (2013). *MetodologiPenelitianPendidikan*. Jakarta: PT BumiAksara

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